

EVOLUTION BEHAVIOR OF TiB WHISKER DURING LASER WELDING IN-SITU SYNTHESIZED TiB/Ti COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, in-situ synthesized titanium matrix composites (TMCs) reinforced with TiB whisker plus La_2O_3 particle were successfully fabricated by the laser beam welding (LBW) process with a Nd:YAG laser source. The evolution behavior of TiB whisker was investigated during laser welding. Optical microscope (OM), X-ray diffractometry (XRD) analysis, scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) were used to analyze the phase, distribution and morphology characteristics of TiB whisker reinforcements in the laser weld seam, and the interface between TiB whiskers (or La_2O_3 particles) and titanium matrix was also discussed. The research results show that TiB whiskers are still retained in the weld, and no harmful substances are found. Compared with the base metal, TiB whiskers are significantly refined and redistribute at β grain boundaries, a novel network structure forms in the fusion zone and the heat-affected zone near the fusion line, which is due to higher heat input of weld thermal cycle. Relatively, only some TiB whiskers in the heat-affected zone far away from the fusion line change their sizes through intensified diffusion of boron because of much lower heat input, and TiB whiskers near the base metal exhibit no changes and similar morphological features with that in the base metal. Further TEM examination proves that interfaces between the reinforcements and the titanium matrix are very clean, and TiB whiskers maintain good bonding relationship with the matrix. No any interfacial reaction is observed, and it explains that interfacial microstructures between the reinforcements and the matrix are very stable during welding, which is beneficial to the mechanical properties of laser welded joints.

1 INTRODUCTION

Recent decades have seen the rapid development of discontinuously reinforced titanium matrix composites (TMCs) which offer an incorporation of good specific strength, durability and metallurgical stability that make them attractive candidate materials for several aspects [1-3]. Especially, reinforcing with TiB whiskers, providing better chemical compatibility with titanium alloys leads to increase the stiffness, fatigue resistance and wear resistance [4]. Besides, additions of rare elements can scavenge the detrimental interstitial oxygen and improve the mechanical properties and heat stability of titanium alloys [5, 6]. Therefore, there have been great interests in $(\text{TiB}+\text{RE}_x\text{O}_y)/\text{Ti}$ composites in the literature [4, 6, 7].

Joining of TMCs is definitely a challenge, and its wide applications in engineering structures have faced many limitations caused by specific characteristics of their joining together or with unreinforced alloys. With nature differences between fillers and matrix, it's basal to produce the physical-chemical traits of joints close to those of base metal by maintenance of the reinforcement code, volume fraction and distribution of fillers in the weld [8]. In order to reduce the likelihood of interface reactions between reinforcements and the matrix in welding TMCs, solid-state methods have the priority, even if various welding ways are available for titanium alloys [9]. Hirose [10] and Antonio [11] discussed the weldability of TMCs using diffusion welding and friction welding respectively.

However, Chernyshov [8] affirmed that high quality joints can be fabricated using the fusion welding methods. Fusion welding is the vitally flexible and versatile joining process and can obtain good joints with favorable mechanical performances, which can broaden the application range of welded structure made of metal matrix composites [12]. Studies on welding titanium alloys with laser beam welding (LBM) and electron beam welding (EBM) were widely explored [13, 14] to produce ideal microstructure and joint strength. During welding TMCs, the weld zone should be minimized to avoid degradation of mechanical properties due to the reinforcement/matrix interface reaction at elevated temperatures. Basing on that, laser beam welding (LBW) seems to be the most suitable for TMCs, because LBW can provide small welding deformation, narrow softening zone [15-17]. Besides, TiB whiskers are *in situ* synthesized in smelting and thermo-mechanically stable as well as reaction-free interfaces with titanium alloys [18]. These described characteristics will enable feasibly welding TMCs using the LBW process. Unluckily, there are few reports on the weldability of the laser-welded joint of discontinuously reinforced TMCs. In this paper, the suitability of laser beam welding of *in situ* synthesized TMCs has been studied, and the behaviors of TiB whiskers in the welded joint have been discussed.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Materials

2.0mm thick sheets used in the paper were Ti-Al-Sn-Zr-Nb-Mo-Si matrix composites reinforced by 1.26 TiB and 0.58 La₂O₃ (vol. %). The reinforcements of TiB and La₂O₃ were *in-situ* synthesized according the reaction between Ti, LaB₆, and oxygen in the raw materials as following:

(TiB+La₂O₃)/Ti composites were made from charges of grade I sponge titanium, LaB₆ powders (>99%, % by weight, hereinafter the same), and raw materials for synthesizing matrix alloy including AlMo, TiSn, AlNb, sponge Zr, pure Al and silicon metal. They were blended by a certain stoichiometric ratio, compacted into electrode and melted into a primary ingot, and then the ingot was remelted twice to make the chemical homogeneity of TMCs. The chemical compositions of TMCs are shown in Table1. After casting, the ingots were hot-forged at 1150°C, then isothermally forged to 30mm thick plate at 1050°C, finally hot-rolled to 2.0mm thick sheets at 1100°C with total reduction of 93%. Rolling stress relief of the sheets has been annealed at 650°C for two hours.

Materials	TiB	La ₂ O ₃	Al	Sn	Zr	Nb	Mo	Si
	vol.%			wt%				
TMCs	1.26	0.582	6.0	3.6	4.1	1.0	0.2	0.34

Table 1: Chemical composition of TMCs

TMCs have a β -transus temperature of 1313K. As shown in Fig.1, the microstructure of base material consists of α equiaxed phases (white) with areas of β phases (grey) at grain boundaries. Some whisker-like substances are dispersed in the matrix. According our earlier studies [4, 6, 7], they are TiB whisker (TiB_w) reinforcements. However, La₂O₃ reinforcements are not observed because they are the nanoscale particles [7].

Fig.1: Optical microstructure of base metal

2.2 LBW processing

In order to obtain the reliable experimental results, TMCs sheets were cut into coupons samples with the same size of 130mm×55mm×2.0mm. Before welding, the required attentions to joint preparation and shielding strategies are necessary. Coupons surfaces were strictly descaled with molten alkaline-based salt bath of (80%NaOH+20%NaNO₃) at 400°C, pickling with 20vol%H₂SO₄ at 60°C and an acid solution composed of 25vol%HNO₃ and 2vol%HF at 50°C, and finally cleaned with acetone.

Without welding wire used, the butt joints were performed perpendicular to the rolling direction of sheets by a TRUMPF LASMA 1054 laser welding facility with a beam diameter of 0.2 mm. The facility is an Nd:YAG continuous laser with a 1.06 mm wavelength (Fig.2).

Argon was used as shielding gas to prohibit the entrance of air to the joint, because titanium has a high affinity to gases including oxygen, nitrogen and hydrogen at temperature over 500°C [9]. The weld was made using an output power of 1.5kW with a travel speed of 1.2m/min. The focal position during LBW was +2.2mm above the top surface of the testpiece.

Fig.2: Schematic diagram of experimental equipment

2.3 Characterization methods

After welding, the joints samples were made via conventional metallographic techniques and etched using Kroll's reagent. The microstructure of the welds and base metal were studied by optical microscope (OM, ZEISS Axio Imager D2m) and scanning electron microscope (SEM, JSM-6460). Room temperature tests (RTT) were conducted for both base metal and joints with sheet specimens. The equipment for RTT was a Zwick/Roell Z020 testing machine at strain rate of $1.2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$. The dimensions for tensile specimens of joints are a gage length of 20mm and a cross-section of 3.2mm×2.0mm.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Weld microstructure

The transverse section for the LBW joint is seen in Fig. 3. Fully penetrated joint was obtained, and the resulting weld shape shows an hourglass form with narrower surface bead width (Fig.3a). The laser weld consists of weld zone (WZ), heat affected zone (HAZ) and base metal (BM). Compared to base metal, the weld zone typically exhibit columnar grains and the microstructure are re fined. Although the weld shows even narrower HAZ compared to GTAW technology [19], further observations reveal that the HAZ of LBW joint display different characteristics due to the welding thermal cycle (Fig.3b).

Fig.3: (a) Cross-section laser beam welds and (b) microstructure of white circle region in (a)

The HAZ near the WZ, named HAZ 1 demonstrates coarse equiaxed grains, which is attributed to the poor thermal conductivity of titanium alloy [9] and the exposure to temperature above the β transus for sufficient length of time. Comparatively, the HAZ far from the WZ, named HAZ 2, shows no visible microstructure changes, similar to that of the base metal.

Moreover, the columnar grains in WZ start by epitaxial growth from HAZ 1 without a nucleation barrier and grow towards the weld center, because the partially melted grains of HAZ 1 provide the non-spontaneous nucleation during the solidification of molten metal bath [20]. Those grains that have their easy growth directions closely aligned with heat flow direction will be favored. Finally, a columnar grain structure occurs. The perpendicularity of columnar grains to the weld centerline is in agreement with this type of solidification. Therefore, the weld thermal cycle and grain size in the HAZ 1 dominates the width of columnar grains in WZ. In other words, the WZ grain size is controlled by the HAZ 1 grain size in the case of epitaxial solidification prevalent in these welds.

Fig.4 shows the X-ray diffraction patterns for the LBW joint compared to the base metal. From Fig.4, It can be known that there are three kinds of phases in the (TiB+La₂O₃)/Ti composites, α' -Ti, TiB and La₂O₃ for the LBW joint, which is similar with the base metal. Comparing with two cures, passes, there is no significant difference in the X-ray diffraction patterns. The only difference in phases between LBW joint and base metal is that the α' -Ti phases in the former substitute for α -Ti in the latter, which is closely related to the LBW process. The results of X-ray diffraction analysis confirm that reinforcement TiB and La₂O₃ are still retained in the weld, and there are no harmful interface reactions during the laser welding process.

Fig.4: X-ray diffraction patterns of the base metal and LBW joint

In the LBW joint, a transition microstructure region from WZ to BM is found, as seen in Fig. 3b and Fig. 5. In the HAZ 2 far from the welding heat source, the HAZ 2 exhibits dissolution of primary α , and the extent of dissolution of primary α gradually decrease far from the WZ. By comparison, the microstructure in HAZ 1 consists of a mixture of martensitic α' , acicular α and primary α (Fig. 5b, c). In addition, the amount of martensitic α' will increase when the HAZ 1 is much closer to the WZ, which is due to the much faster cooling rate. This phenomenon corresponds to a sample quenched from temperature below the β transus. On subsequent rapid cooling of the weld below the β transus temperature, the diffusionless transformation ($\beta \rightarrow \alpha$) take place. The acicular microstructures in WZ and HAZ 1 could not be clearly resolved using a metallurgic microscope (Fig.3). Further examinations of the structure by SEM (Fig. 5) indicate that the martensitic α' , corresponding to a structure quenched from above the β transus temperature, constitutes the microstructure of WZ and HAZ 1. Martensites α' intersect each other like a basket-weave structure [21]. The martensite lath size is finer, and the α' plates are longer due to higher cooling rate at high speed welding. The acicular product of hexagonal martensite (α') in WZ is confirmed by TEM analysis (Fig.6a). Besides, La₂O₃ reinforcements still keep good bonding relationship, and no desirable interface compounds can be observed (Fig.6c)

Fig.5: SEM images of welded joints: (a) WZ; (b) WZ-HAZ 1; (c) HAZ 1-HAZ 2 (d) HAZ 2-BM

3.2 Formation and mechanism of TiB in weld

As shown in Fig.3, some black substances are redistributed at β columnar grain boundaries in the WZ and HAZ 1, forming a network structure due to the grain refinement. This phenomenon is further proved by SEM observations (Fig.5). The enlarged images reveal that they are TiB_w reinforcements (Figs. 7a, b) and verified by EDS analysis (Fig.7c). For the EDS results, it should be pointed out that the extra diffraction peaks of Al can be due to the aluminum element in the matrix.

Fig. 6: TEM image of WZ: (a) martensitic structure, (b) TiB whisker and (c) La_2O_3 reinforcements

Fig. 7 higher magnification SEM images of WZ, HAZ 1, EDS for rectangle area of (a) and (b)

The research results reveal that laser beam welding play an important role in TiB whiskers, both their distribution and sizes. As mentioned above, during laser welding TMCs, reinforcement TiB_w were kept in the weld. In WZ and HAZ 1, TiB_w redistribute at β columnar grain boundaries, and they are smaller sizes and show a few clusters. The aspect ratio of TiB_w in WZ and HAZ 1 with 20~22 is much larger than that of BM (4~5). Enlarged SEM images reveal that TiB_w display a needle shaped morphology (Fig.5 and Fig.7), and develop into a network-like structure. Interestingly, in HAZ 1, TiB_w seem to be divided into parts from a single whisker, shown by A and B in Fig.4b and become thin and longer. This shape change, which may reveal the revolution of TiB_w during the laser welding, can be ascribed to the welding thermal cycle. In HAZ 2 far from the heat resource, TiB_w show no distinct changes and might partially become smaller or decomposed through intensified diffusion of boron due to the effect of thermal cycle. TEM examination proves that reinforcements TiB_w and La₂O₃ are retained in the weld and maintain good bonding relationship with the matrix during welding, and no undesirable interface reactions or interfacial cracking is found (Fig. 6b, c).

The heat resource temperature of laser beam welding with high energy density is much higher than the melting point (2473 K) of TiB_w [22], and TiB_w in WZ are thoroughly dissolved in the molten pool. While the weld pool starts to solidify, rapid solidification (RS) of liquid titanium containing boron results in the supersaturated solid solution, because boron has a very low solid solubility in titanium [23]. In this study, boron concentration (0.3wt %) in TMCs is below the eutectic point, thus the prior β phases first appears according to the Ti-B binary phase diagram [24]. Once the formation of prior β phases, the enriched solutes cause constitutional supercooling, and TiB_w precipitate on subsequent consolidation of the RS products. In addition, TiB_w has a crystal orientation relationship with titanium, therefore, the compatible β -Ti/ β -Ti interfaces provide an energetic priority nucleation site for TiB [25], and this will cause the formation of numerous TiB nuclei. At the same time, rapid cooling will reduce the growth rate of TiB_w. Afterwards, TiB_w grow at β grain boundaries in the weld with smaller sizes in WZ and HAZ 1.

4. CONCLUSIONS

1. The microstructure of TMCs consists of a phases with areas of b phases at grain boundaries. *In situ* TiB_w reinforcements uniformly distribute in the matrix.
2. *In-situ* synthesized titanium matrix composites with 2.0 mm thickness can be successfully joined by laser beam welding process without filler metal used, and the well quality joints were obtained.
3. In WZ, the microstructure exhibits refined columnar grains, and coarse equiaxed grains are found in HAZ 1. The WZ and near HAZ 1 consists of a' martensite. The HAZ 2 consists of a' martensite and primary a phases.
4. In situ TiB_w are still retained in the LBW joint, and no undesirable interface reactions are found between the whisker and matrix. TiB_w, having smaller sizes, redistribute at prior β grain boundaries to form the network structure in WZ and HAZ 1, and they display a more dispersed distribution in HAZ 2.

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